

FEATURES OF THE COURSE OF OXALATE NEPHROPATHIES IN CHILDREN WITH CONNECTIVE TISSUE DYSPLASIA

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Abstract. *This article presents the results of a study on the clinical manifestations of connective tissue dysplasia (CTD) in children with oxalate nephropathies. A total of 55 children aged 3 to 16 years were examined, of whom 22 patients were diagnosed with dysmetabolic nephropathy, and 33 with chronic pyelonephritis of dysmetabolic and mixed origin. A comprehensive analysis was performed of external phenotypic signs, musculoskeletal and visceral manifestations of dysplastic syndrome, as well as their association with the clinical and laboratory features of oxalate nephropathy. It was found that a significant proportion of patients exhibited signs of systemic connective tissue dysplasia of varying severity, including joint hypermobility, posture abnormalities, skeletal system anomalies, visual pathology, and cardiovascular and hemostatic changes. The severity of dysplastic disorders was higher in children with chronic pyelonephritis of dysmetabolic and mixed origin. The data highlight the importance of assessing phenotypic and systemic signs of CTD for optimizing the diagnosis and management of children with oxalate nephropathies.*

Keywords: *oxalate nephropathy; hyperoxaluria; dysmetabolic nephropathy; connective tissue dysplasia; phenotypic signs; joint hypermobility; chronic pyelonephritis; children.*

Introduction. Connective tissue developmental disorders in children include a significant proportion of non-differentiated dysplasias, which, according to current literature, occur in 13–25% of the pediatric population. This pathology is considered a complex genetically determined syndrome associated with dysfunction of various organs and systems. Of particular interest is the combination of CTD with urological diseases, particularly oxalate nephropathy, characterized by oxalate metabolism disorders, a tendency to nephrocalcinosis, recurrent urinary tract infections, and progression of chronic inflammatory processes.

The clinical course of oxalate nephropathies in children is largely determined by the state of connective tissue, since structural changes in it contribute to the formation of anomalies in the urinary system, urodynamic disorders, diffuse metabolic shifts, and involvement of the cardiovascular and musculoskeletal systems. Phenotypic signs of dysplasia are often associated with mineral metabolism changes, joint hypermobility, posture defects, decreased muscle tone, and impaired tissue trophism, which can exacerbate oxaluria and influence the clinical presentation.

According to numerous studies, among many anomalies, non-differentiated connective tissue defects are most common, often referred to as the “minor” connective tissue dysplasia syndrome. In recent years, involvement of various organs and systems in mild forms of dysplasia has been actively studied. The most well-studied are manifestations in the cardiovascular system, joints, spine, gastrointestinal tract, and hemostasis system. Literature contains isolated reports on the association of CTD signs with oxaluria. Oxaluria itself reflects increased excretion of oxalic

acid, the end product of metabolism of compounds such as glycine, serine, and hydroxyproline, which play an important role in connective tissue metabolism.

Objective: To study the clinical manifestations of connective tissue dysplasia in children with oxalate nephropathies.

Materials and Methods. The study included 55 children aged 3–16 years with oxalate-calcium crystalluria and hyperoxaluria. The mean disease duration was 1–4 years. The control group consisted of 30 healthy children without urinary system diseases. Inclusion criteria: recurrent crystalluria, dysmetabolic nephropathy, or chronic pyelonephritis of dysmetabolic and mixed origin, persistent urinary sediment changes. Exclusion criteria: congenital anomalies of kidney and urinary tract development. All patients underwent clinical, anamnesis, and ultrasound examinations. Phenotypic signs of CTD were assessed, including spine and joint status, chest shape, hypermobility, recurvation, posture, muscle tone, and cardiovascular and visual systems. Additionally, Beighton and Carter–Wilkinson tests, laboratory kidney function tests, echocardiography, and urine mineral analysis were performed. Statistical analysis used the χ^2 test.

Results and Discussion. Among children with oxaluria: dysmetabolic nephropathy (DMN) — 22 (40.2%) and chronic pyelonephritis (CPN) of dysmetabolic and mixed origin — 33 (59.8%). Clinical data showed that external signs of CTD were present in both groups but with varying frequency. The most common manifestations were high-arched palate — 16 (29.6%), finger tremor — 17 (30.4%) ($p < 0.001$), and auricle anomalies — 7 (12.0%). Dysplastic skeletal changes were less frequent in DMN compared to CPN, consistent with a trend toward more pronounced CTD changes in inflammatory forms. Postural disorders and muscle hypotonia were observed in 41 (74.4%) children, and joint hypermobility — in 35 (64.0%). The most frequent joint hypermobility phenomenon was elbow recurvation — 44 (80.0%); least frequent was positive dorsiflexion test of the foot — 12 (21.6%). Spine involvement, including posture disorders, scoliosis, and cervical instability, was more common in children with oxaluria than in healthy peers ($p < 0.001$). Joint abnormalities — hip dysplasia in history, reactive arthritis episodes, arthralgia — were also significantly more frequent ($p < 0.05$). Within-group analysis showed musculoskeletal changes were more common in CPN than DMN. Children with CPN had more frequent spine and joint involvement, correlating with more pronounced CTD changes in inflammatory nephropathy forms. A more severe systemic dysplastic background was indicated by involvement of five or more organ systems, predominantly in the CPN group ($p < 0.01$). Pathological kidney mobility was noted in 36% of children with oxaluria, considered a manifestation of CTD.

Cardiovascular abnormalities were found in 69.6% of children; echocardiography showed structural anomalies in 44 (79.3%), including additional trabeculae in the left ventricle — 32 (57.2%) and mitral valve prolapse — 14 (25.3%). In the control group, such changes occurred in only 16.7%. Ophthalmological abnormalities typical of CTD, such as refractive disorders and progressive vision impairment, were more frequent. Hemostatic system changes included platelet disorders and recurrent epistaxis, noted in 14 (24.8%) children versus 2% in controls ($p < 0.001$). According to the T. Milyukovskaya–Dmitrova and A. Karkasheva classification, dysplasia severity: DMN — moderate in 1 (3.4%); CPN — 6 (18.2%) ($p < 0.05$). This indicates more pronounced underdevelopment of urinary system connective tissue elements in inflammatory nephropathy, predisposing to bacterial or aseptic inflammation.

Clinical Case. Patient A., 11 years old, presented with recurrent abdominal pain, mainly in the right iliac region, episodic small-volume urination, nausea, appetite reduction, constipation

and macroscopic hematuria episodes over 1.5 years. History: frequent URIs, cystitis episodes; symptoms since age 9, exacerbated by physical activity; previous outpatient treatment for dysmetabolic nephropathy; unremarkable birth and development; positive family history for CTD (mother — mitral valve prolapse).

Objective: asthenic build, body weight below age norm, thin skin, joint hypermobility (Beighton score 6), elbow recurvation, flat-valgus feet, posture disorders, muffled heart sounds, systolic murmur at apex.

Ultrasound: moderate right pelvicalyceal dilatation, increased parenchymal echogenicity, echogenic inclusions up to 3 mm, signs of pyelonephritis, pathological mobility of right kidney.

Urinalysis: mild proteinuria (0.1–0.15 g/L), microhematuria, leukocyturia 10–12/hpf, oxalate-calcium crystalluria.

Biochemistry: elevated oxalates, decreased citrate. Echocardiography: left ventricle additional trabeculae, mitral valve prolapse grade I, moderate right atrial dilatation. Orthopedic and cardiology consultation: asthenic syndrome, moderate CTD, spine statics disorder. Recommended: physiotherapy, orthopedic regimen, cardiologist follow-up.

Diagnosis:

Oxalate nephropathy, recurrent course; nondifferentiated CTD, moderate severity; joint hypermobility; mitral valve prolapse I; kidney mobility; mineral metabolism disorder.

Treatment:

Oxalate-restricted diet, citrate therapy, phytotherapy, normalization of fluid intake, prevention of urinary infections, metabolic therapy, correction of mineral metabolism.

Follow-up:

After 3 months — symptom reduction, decreased crystalluria, normalized urination frequency, reduced pain.

Conclusion. This case illustrates the systemic nature of CTD, influencing the course of oxalate nephropathy, the variety of clinical manifestations, and the importance of a comprehensive management approach.

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